

A Novel Method for Leaf Identification using Machine Learning

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Abstract

Plants play a very important role for sustenance of life on earth. The leaf of a plant is one of the significant factors to identify various plant characteristics like their species, health and even the climate. The growing interest in biodiversity and the increasing availability of digital images help us to review and analyze plant leaf. We use features like leaf outlines, shape, vein structures and textures and use wide range of analytical methods to describe the mentioned characteristics. We use image processing techniques for a set of training images to generate the feature vectors. Once the machine is trained, we apply test images for feature detection and classification of the plant species. Application of this method can be used in prototypes of hand-held digital field guides and various robotic systems in agriculture. We conclude with a discussion of ongoing work and challenging problems in this area.

Keywords: Image processing, leaf analysis, robotic systems, identifying characteristics, detection of species, digital field guide.

Introduction

The classification of leafs is very important in grouping leaves into different ranks and classes based on different classifiers or categories. It puts each group of leafs having some common properties into classes. Also the classes are then divided into sub-classes and types to differentiate among the elements of the class. This classification is very important to help scientists to study the common behaviors and properties of the leaves. Especially those leafs. Used in the medicine or medical leafs.

In the past before the invention of digital cameras and computerized systems, people were using their own absolute experience in defining different types of medical plants. The risk of using the wrong leafs for medicine extraction increases with the lack of experience and can cause fatal error that can cause the death of some patients.

The existence of digital devices and possibilities of computer vision has encouraged the botanists and computer scientists to develop computerized systems or semi automatic systems for leafs

classification or recognition based on different features. Different researches have treated the problems of the leaves classification and mentioned different methods of recognition for these plants. The last century has seen a very great development in artificial intelligence and machine vision where a lots of pattern recognition and classification tasks were investigated by using automatic computer systems.

Objectives

The shape of leaves can be used to identify species and define species boundaries. Digital images of plants are increasingly available. Image processing challenges include object deformations, a large number of classes, and a large numbers of features to be selected. By knowing the feature of a leaf we can come to know that what the purpose of using that leaf in short span of time.

Image Pre-Processing

A typical image based plant identification system is shown and the major steps are explained in consecutive sub-sections.

Flow diagram of proposed scheme

Image acquisition

A leaf image can be easily captured using scanner or digital camera. The image can be of different size. However, for good results, the image should have preferably single colour background with no blurriness'. The proposed system is checked on Flavia database which contains 1907 RGB leaves images of 33 plants; each species has forty to sixty sample leaves. Each image in dataset is of 1600x 1200 resolutions having white background and with no leafstalk. File names of all images are 4-digit numbers, "and mandatory to add .jpg"

Preprocessing

In order to take out any specific information, image preprocessing steps are carried out before the actual analysis of the image data. Preprocessing refers to the initial processing of input leaf image to abolish the noise and accurate the degraded data. Images adorn techniques like grayscale, conversion, binarization, smoothing, filtering, edge detection, etc. used for the enhancement of the leaf image.

Feature extraction

Our procedure takes into describe the color and shape attribute of the leaf. Leaves of different plants are invariably similar in color and shapes therefore a single feature alone may not give anticipate results.

Color features

The procedure of image observant and retrieval proposed by Dr. H.B. Kerri mainly concentrated on the generation of the color feature vector by calculating the average means. In the proposed problem, first the three color planes namely Red, Green and Blue are unrelated. Then for each flat line of colors are calculated. The average of total row and total columns means is calculated for each plane. The features of all 3 planes are combined to form a feature vector. Once the feature vectors are produced for an image, they are deposited in a database.

Shape features

We defined shape features on the basis of morphological features and tooth features:

Geometric features

We used the alike commonly used 5 geometric features {DMFs}, illustrated is extracted from following 5 basic attributes:

1. **Diameter:** The diameter of the leaf is the height between any two points on the closed contour of the leaf.
2. **Physiological Length:** It is the length of the line connecting the two end points of the main vein in the leaf.
3. **Physiological Width:** It refers to the space between the two end points of the longest line segment perpendicular to the physiological height length and breadth”.
4. **Leaf Area:** It is the number of pixels resolution of binary value 1 on smoothed leaf image.
5. **Leaf Perimeter:** It is the number of pixels along the closed outline of the leaf.

Morphological Features

Based on above 5 fundamental geometric attributes, we can define following 12 digital morphological attribute:

- **Aspect Ratio:** This is defined as the ratio of physiological length to physiological width that is length/width.
- **Form Factor:** It is defined as the changes between a leaf and a circle and is calculated by the formula $4\pi A/P^2$.
- **Rectangularity:** It narrate how similar a leaf is to a rectangle and is computed as $L \cdot \text{Width}/\text{area}$
- **Narrow Factor:** It determines the straightness of the leaf and is calculated as $\text{Diameter}/\text{Length}$.
- **Perimeter Ratio of Diameter:** It is defined as the ratio of the perimeter of the leaf to the diameter of the leaf, i.e., P/D .
- **Vein Features:** Leaf vein forms the fundamental of leaf characterization and classification as they detail the skeletal structure of the leaf. Different variety has different leaf vein patterns which can be used in distinguishing the leaves that have similar shape. The standard method for computing the vein features is to perform a morphological opening operation on the grayscale image. A plane, disk shaped structured element of radius 1,2,3,4 is used and the

resultant image is then subtracted from the contour of the leaf. The result resembles to the vein structure of the leaves on the basis of which following 5 vein features are calculated:” $A1/A$, $A2/A$, $A3/A$, $A4/A$, $A4/A1$ where A_r is the remaining leaf acquire using a structuring element of radius r and A is the area of the leaf.

Classification, Training & Testing

Extensive statistical classification is the action of identifying a set of group of leafs, or classes, to which a new survey belongs, on the basis of preliminary knowledge such as a training dataset. More specifically, category in this work will be the process used to assign a certain leaf species to an image, based on its feature set., namely supervised learning. We formalize the classification elements as follows:

Classifier Selection

We obeyed two approaches to classify our datasets, which are Neural Networks and Euclidean Distance Method.

A neural network, illustrated consists of units

{Neurons}, placed in layers, which convert an input data into some outputs. Each unit takes an input, applies a {often nonlinear} function to it and then forwards the output on to the next layer. Generally the networks are defined to be move forward: a unit feeds its output to all the units on the next unit, but there is no connection between the previous layers. Weightings are applied to the signals passing from one layer to another layer, and it is these weightings which are tuned in the training stage to adapt a neural network to the particular problem at hand. This is the learning stage.

Training & Testing

Flavia dataset contains a total of 1907 images of 33 different plant types. These images were used to train the classifiers. For each type of plant’s leaf in flavia dataset, we selected 5 species of leaves from pilot sets which are then used to test the accuracy of the suggested algorithm in terms of efficiency and implementation time.

Conclusion

This paper introduces a neural network approach for plant leaf recognition. The computer can automatically classify thirty two kinds of plants via the leaf images loaded from digital cameras Or scanners. PNN is adopted for it has fast speed on training and simple structure. Twelve features are extracted and processed by PCA to form the input vector of PNN. Experimental result. Indicates that our algorithm is workable with accuracy than ninety percent on thirty two kinds of plants. Compared with other methods, this algorithm is fast in execution, efficient in Recognition and easy in implementation. Future work is under consideration to improve it.

Wed Sources

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